

NESTORE

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Communication and dissemination plan

DELIVERABLE 1.3

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Short Abstract

Deliverable 1.3 aims to present the plan for the dissemination of the NESTORE project results, in order to ensure that they will effectively reach the widest audience possible. Thus D1.3 defines the dissemination strategy incorporating the objectives, target groups and communication channels. Moreover, it provides information about target publications in journals/conferences, target events (including those to be organised) and other complementary dissemination actions and evaluation.

Key Words

Dissemination plan, dissemination strategy, journals, conferences, workshops, clustering activities.

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1. Executive summary

Deliverable 1.3 aims to present the plan for the dissemination of the NESTORE project results, in order to ensure that they will effectively reach the widest audience possible. Thus D1.3 defines the dissemination strategy incorporating the objectives, target groups and communication channels. Moreover, it provides information about target publications in journals/conferences, target events (including those to be organised) and other complementary dissemination actions and evaluation.

Deliverable D1.3 reports on the dissemination policy, activities and channels of the European Commission funded project NESTORE. It defines the dissemination strategy, reminds the core dissemination principles and visibility rules, and identifies the relevant audiences to target and the appropriate channels to use in order to reach them. It also provides information about target publications in journals/conferences, target events (including those to be organised) and other complementary dissemination actions. Finally, it aims to guide partners on how to take dissemination initiatives in the frame of NESTORE and how to report on their activities.

The project will follow different phases from awareness-raising to engagement of external stakeholders and promotion of potential exploitation output around key milestones. Together with communication channels, the report includes a list of indicators and a template for monitoring the communication activities. The dissemination plan will be updated regularly according to the project work progress; amendments, new activities and assets (if any) will be reported in the dissemination reports (D1.5) at M18 and M36.

2. Introduction

To ensure the effective dissemination of the NESTORE activities and results, a specific task, i.e., “T1.4 – Communication and Dissemination Management” was included in the work plan of the project. This deliverable is one of the first outcomes of this Task; it aims to outline the dissemination strategy and present the activities to be addressed to both the scientific community and the wide public. This plan also proposes communication assets based on D1.2 – Project Website and D1.4 Communication Toolkit that will help informing the general public, build a network of relevant stakeholders and foster penetration of NESTORE in the relevant sectors.

To this end, deliverable D1.3 presents the dissemination strategy, incorporating the objectives and the target audiences that NESTORE wants to reach and the means that will be used to accomplish it. Then, the different dissemination assets made available to consortium members and external partners (including media) are described as well as specific activities that will be used to reach the various target audiences, i.e., publications, participation in events, organisation of events and clustering activities. At last, the dissemination evaluation process is outlined. The dissemination activities and results will be reported in detail in three communication and dissemination reports (D1.5) as well as in the regular project periodic reports.

As Task leader, AGE Platform Europe is responsible for the overall communication and dissemination strategy with the support of the project coordinator, POLIMI. NEOS being responsible for developing the project brand and identify, the present deliverable was developed in synergies with the elaboration of the project website (D1.2) and first communication toolkit (D1.4) that will be regularly updated and fed with new communication assets as the project moves forward. Finally, all partners contributed to this plan by providing input to AGE in terms of communication channels and listing publications or events that are foreseen by partners in the frame of their contribution to the NESTORE project in the technical work packages (WP).

3. Dissemination strategy

The ultimate aim of NESTORE, as an ICT-based health project, is the development of Novel Empowering Solutions and Technologies for Older people to Retain Everyday life activities. Dissemination will thus play a key role in the society wide, large-scale utilisation of a system that significantly enhances health as people age. This requires proven health benefits and user acceptance of the technology, viable commercialisation opportunities, and penetration into societal communities and health and care systems.

Dissemination activities will be deeply interlaced with the structure of the different work packages. Communication and dissemination management will be dealt with at strategic level as a Task, within the management work package (WP1) while at operational level each work package will contribute to the scientific dissemination, according to targets in terms of impact factors and relevance of events and publication opportunities defined by WP1.

3.1. Objectives

3.1.1. Overall objective

Dissemination strategies will be tailored to the different phase of the project, from the early stages where the focus will be on raising awareness about the project and its aims, throughout its entire duration to ensure timely release of updates on research findings to the closing phase where strategies will be aimed at ensuring proper exploitation of the project results. Some concrete objectives of the overall NESTORE dissemination strategy can be defined as follows:

1. Empower final users and relevant stakeholders, so to be part of the research that is meant for them and that will be steered by their inputs, preferences and needs;
2. Offer visibility to the system and involve end users and stakeholders in providing feedback complementarily to and in support of user involvement activities as part of the project development process and foreseen in the frame of WP7;
3. Offer visibility to the project to inform all stakeholders and possibly involve potential partners (may they be industrial or institutional) for the exploitation phase to be organised jointly with the work performed under WP8;
4. Communication the final results of the project to (1) a wider audience using plain and national languages as much as possible and (2) the scientific community.

These objectives will drive external dissemination activities. However, it should be noted here that the above will only be made possible if an internal project understanding of NESTORE outcomes and progress is created to motivate all partners to disseminate the project to their own stakeholders and networks. Internal communication and information sharing processes are described in the Project Management Plan (D1.1 – confidential to the consortium only).

3.1.2. Dissemination plan adaptation

All partners will spread NESTORE results participating in national and international conferences. In the first year, project presentations will concentrate mainly on the project goals and vision. Presentations of research results will come in the following years of the project. The dissemination plan will be adapted according to the project work progress; amendments, new activities and assets (if any) will be reported in the dissemination reports (D1.5) at M18 and M36.

3.2. Budget and rules

3.2.1. Budget

NESTORE being a European Commission funded project, partners have a dedicated budget to implement communication and dissemination activities. They also have to follow specific rules that are clarified below. Rules are stated in the project Grant agreement and in the Consortium agreement. We summarize here the main aspects. Besides the 16 person/months (PM) split among project partners to work on project management, dissemination and communication strategy under work package 1 (WP1), all partners are expected to contribute to dissemination activities in the frame of their activities in the technical work packages.

The work effort planned under WP7, covering co-design and pilot experiments (129 person / months) and WP8 dedicated to exploitation, stakeholder involvement and development of business model (58,5 person / months) will be particularly useful for the achievement of the dissemination objectives. Dissemination is supported with dedicated budget for open access publications, organisation of events, printing of dissemination material and translation. Budget for these other direct costs is allocated to POLIMI, AGE and NEOS.

3.2.2. EU communication rules

Article 29 of the Grant Agreement¹ states the rules regarding the dissemination of results; it reminds that “unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must: (a) display the EU emblem and, (b) include the following text: ‘This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769643’. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence” (article 29.4). The Grant Agreement also reminds the existence of a disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility: “Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains” (article 29.5).

3.2.3. Confidentiality policy

Article 36 of the Grant Agreement explains the rules related to confidentiality. The general rule is the following: “During implementation of the action and for four years after the period set out in Article 3, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at the time it is disclosed (“confidential information”)” (article 36.1). Many of the NESTORE deliverables have a restricted dissemination level – CO standing for Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services). Partners are invited to refer to the Project proposal with the list of deliverables², together with the dissemination policy attached to it, and the Consortium Agreement for more information on confidentiality policies.

3.2.4. Accessibility

Accessibility – that is access to content by everyone regardless of abilities – is a key principle of NESTORE dissemination activities. As a matter of fact, key target groups of the project’s dissemination are likely to experience accessibility challenges stemming from old age, illness or disability. Thus the project will ensure the widest readability, comprehensibility and affordability of all project dissemination activities and channels via the visual supports (incl. photographs, infographics, videos, etc.) use of plain language, and users and pilot

¹ All quotes in the paragraph are from: NESTORE Grant Agreement, page 48.

² NESTORE Project proposal, pages 117 and 118.

participants' mother tongue. The diversification of channels and dissemination tools, both physical and digital ones, will be of utmost importance to reach a wide variety of people with different background, especially among the end user group.

3.2.5. Ethics and gender aspects

NESTORE dissemination activities will be aligned with the ethical approach that will be defined within WP8. Gender aspects will be integrated from the beginning of all activities through the work of WP2 that will develop a gender sensitive model and WP7 that will adopt a gender lens in the development of a co-design process. The NESTORE partners will adopt a gender-sensitive dissemination approach especially in the selection of images that will counterbalance the project logo depicting a man. The writing guidelines available in Annex I specify to gender-sensitive communication rules.

3.3. Target audiences

There are different types of identified target audiences for NESTORE, such as older persons, their relatives, health and care professionals, scientific communities (mainly in the field of health and wellness and health promotion, ageing, disease prevention, health technologies), policy makers, media, social workers, etc. These different types of audiences fall into three categories of stakeholders: wide public, scientific, social and commercial.

For this reason, NESTORE, in addition to the traditional scientific dissemination oriented at promoting the underlying technological advances towards the academic and research communities, will also make use of marketing communication techniques in order to better engage the target community and the key stakeholders to develop awareness about NESTORE as a product and develop an ecosystem of stakeholders around the project.

3.3.1. Wide public and potential end users

The first dissemination strategies will be designed specifically taking into consideration the primary target audience of NESTORE: end users. It is indeed of paramount importance that the communication campaign towards older people is carefully crafted. A range of different end-users can be identified for digital solutions supporting active and healthy ageing. The Active and Assisted Living (AAL) funding programme thus suggest three sub-groups³:

1. Primary users: individuals who use the digital product or service for ageing well. This group benefits directly from the solution through experiencing increased quality of life;
2. Secondary users: people or organisations in direct contact with primary users, such as formal and informal carers, family members, friends, neighbours, and care organisations representatives. This user group benefits directly from the solution, and indirectly when primary users' needs for health care and social care are reduced;
3. Tertiary users: institutions and private or public organisations that do not use directly solutions supporting active and healthy ageing, but that organise, pay for, or enable them. These include public sector service organisers, social security systems and insurance companies. They benefit from the increased efficiency and effectiveness that digital solutions for active and healthy ageing bring in service provision.

³ <http://www.aal-europe.eu/get-involved/i-am-a-user-2/>

3.3.2. Scientific communities

Specific groups within the scientific community are expected to show the highest interest; these are scientists within the field of active and healthy ageing, health promotion, disease and frailty prevention, health technologies, mobile health applications, serious games, signal/image processing and pattern recognition. The purpose of addressing these groups is to generate grants, collaboration opportunities, technological development and translation to health services.

Links with specialised research centres and communities around key European and national funded projects involved in activities related to NESTORE will also be established in order to exchange research results and experiences in the field of mutual interest, avoid replication of work and maximise dissemination results.

3.3.3. Commercial stakeholders

This audience is constituted of Research and Development (R&D) departments of businesses that could be interested in the uptake and commercialisation of NESTORE outcomes. They may be sensor manufacturers, software developers, providers of supportive interventions technologies, insurances, and other private health providers that will be interested in exploiting certain modules of the project, with respect to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues, in order to enrich their arsenal.

3.3.4. Policy stakeholders

Public authorities are one of the main players when it comes to the provision of health and social care provision. Trying to prevent age-related impairments and frailty, some local authorities have developed age-friendly environments; most of them are gathering under the World Health Organisation (WHO) Global Network of Age-Friendly Cities and Communities (GNAFCC)⁴ or the European Covenant on Demographic Change⁵. The involvement of public authorities will also play a crucial role when it comes to ensuring that the NESTORE coach is retained as a mainstream service and its upscaling and replication considered.

At European level, support of policy making processes on supra-national level will be one of NESTORE key dissemination goals driven by the release of policy recommendations towards the end of the project. Interaction with different policy and networking groups will ensure that NESTORE results are exploited at EU level and inform policy making and other related projects. We consider getting in touch with the following:

1. the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP on AHA)⁶ action groups on functional decline and frailty (A3) and integrated care (B3);
2. the European Parliament intergroup on Active ageing, intergenerational solidarity & family policies⁷, especially the sub-intergroup on Active ageing;
3. the European Commission eHealth stakeholder group⁸;
4. the European Commission relevant Directorate-Generals, especially DG SANTE (Health and Food Safety) and DG CNECT (Communications Networks, Content and Technology) as well as the Research Executive Agency.

⁴ http://www.who.int/ageing/projects/age_friendly_cities_network/en/

⁵ <http://agefriendlyeurope.org/>

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/actiongroup_en

⁷ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/aboutparliament/en/20150201PVL00010/Organisation#intergroups>

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ehealth-stakeholder-group-members>

3.3.5. Press

Unlike many of the aforementioned target groups which are likely to be reached by means of blog posts, journals/conferences and industry events or networking activities, media present a less cohesive and focused group. The media plays an important role in public education and policy making though, and cannot be overlooked in that context. Thus, several press releases will be issued over the course of the project. The following media have already been identified as potential interested press partners:

Table 1 - Preliminary list of target media

GENERAL	EU Observer (EU), Euractiv (EU), European Voice (EU), Reuters (UK)
AGEING	Age Economie (FR), Senior Actu (FR), Choice Mag (UK), SAGA Magazine (UK)
ICT	HIMSS Insights (EU), Digital Single Market newsroom (EU), Euronews Futuris (EU), Exame Informatica (ES), BBC CLICK (UK), Make, Create, Innovate CNN (UK)
HEALTH	International Association of Gerontology and Geriatrics (EU), HealthManagement (EU), e-health-com (EU), ehealthnews (EU), Healthcare Mediportal (DE), Digital Health Digest (UK)
RESEARCH	Horizon2020 (EU), CORDIS (EU), InsightScience (NL)

3.4. Implementation of dissemination activities

3.4.1. Dissemination planning

In order for these objectives to be satisfied, each consortium member is fully committed to the targeted dissemination of results across the ecosystem of stakeholders, and within their own strategy. Dissemination will take place at multiple levels and all partners will contribute via the routes that are most appropriate to their operational model and expertise. Generally, dissemination activities will be designed developed and planned answering the following questions: Who (target audience), What (key messages), When (timing), Why (expected outcomes), How (communication assets or channels), By whom (responsible partner for the dissemination activity).

The implementation of the dissemination plan will follow an evolving process, from a wider awareness raising to a more targeted dissemination to experts and potential interested stakeholders on the project results. Three phases are presented below; while the first one proposes consistent actions for the first project year, the two others only suggest preliminary ideas to be updated in later stages when the project delivers its first results.

3.4.2. First phase: M0 to M4 – Planning

This phase aimed to prepare the dissemination and communication activities with the development of the present dissemination plan as well as the set up of an initial communication toolkit that is presented more extensively in Part 2. Dissemination channels and tools. This phase was designed based on a first discussion with project partners at the Kick-Off Meeting on what values and images should NESTORE provide to the wider

public, and what was initially proposed in the NESTORE project submission phase. We thus ended up with the following. By the time the dissemination plan is released, some partners will already have introduced the project at several events:

1. 1 to 3 December 2017: participation of POLIMI to the Maker Faire⁹ in Rome, Italy
2. 23 and 24 January 2018: participation of AGE Platform Europe to the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing¹⁰ – Action Group A3 meeting on Functional Decline and Frailty in Twente, Netherlands.

By the end of the first phase, the kick-off of the dissemination activities will be organised following the delivery of the “Kick-off development phase” first project milestone (MS01) that the due date is the end of November 2017 (M3). The very first activity will thus be a dissemination campaign to start from January 2018 on (M5) with the launch of the project website. This campaign will be structured around a press release to be issued to a list of specialised media and organisations or institutions interested in NESTORE fields of research and innovation; several publications will follow on relevant partners’ channels (e.g. organisation website, newsletters and social media) to inform about the project objectives and expected results.

Key actions during the first phase:

1. Release of the project website
2. Press release #1 (M05) – “Project website goes live!”
3. Publication of articles about the project through relevant partners’ channels

3.4.3. Second phase: M5 to M12 (year 1) – Raising Awareness

The second phase is focused on a wide awareness raising, i.e. informing the general public and potential users on the existence of NESTORE, the objectives it aims to achieve and the way external stakeholders – including future users – are invited to contribute and give their feedback. This initial dissemination phase will be critical to build a clear understanding of what is NESTORE to the highest and most diversified number of stakeholders as possible. The accessibility is a principle that will have to be carefully followed all along the project but particularly in this preliminary awareness raising phase.

The second phase will follow different sub-objectives that we plan to achieve by the implementation of different dissemination activities:

1. Improving the level and quality of information disseminated through the project communication tools: e.g. updating the website with news and events, feeding the social media accounts with regular posts about the project work progress or developments in the research and innovation fields of NESTORE, issuing newsletters and press releases on the occasion of the delivery of major project milestones or output, etc.;
2. Improving the visibility of the project through the identification of and participation to key events (within the limits of the project budget), using the project templates and flyers or any dissemination tools necessary to the visibility of NESTORE;
3. Increasing the number of website visits, registrations to the newsletter and the number of followers on social media to a significant level.

Specific dissemination activities will seek to mark milestones in the project over this period:

⁹ <http://www.makerfairerome.eu/en/>

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/home_en

1. MS02 – 1st Intermediate Integration Workshop; due date: M09. This second milestone will be the occasion of a physical meeting and will lead to the release of the first system prototype. These integration workshops will bring together developers in one location to perform actual integration of different components. A prototype will be release at the end of each integration workshop giving an opportunity to update the NESTORE followers, readers and interested stakeholders with the project latest technical developments. These news will have to be “translated” into different formats and languages to ensure the accessibility of the information and address target audiences with different interests and levels of expertise.
2. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 2.1. Article on the project website and/or update of the “Technology” section;
 - 2.2. Issue of a press release to specialised press and media;
 - 2.3. Issue of a project newsletter to inform about the project objectives;
 - 2.4. Social media posts promoting the article and press release
3. MS03 – End of Year 1 and first Forum of Advisory Stakeholders (FAS) meeting; due date: M12.
4. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 4.1. Interview(s) of FAS members on the project website;
 - 4.2. Issue of a project newsletter (incl. other news and events);
 - 4.3. Social media posts promoting the article and newsletter.
5. The organisation of a public event with both the general and local Forum of Advisory Stakeholders as well as interested third parties could be considered depending on the work progress of the research and development activities and the budget available.

Key actions during the first phase:

1. Publication of regular news and events on the project website
2. Publication of regular posts on social media accounts
3. Press release #2 (M09) – First integration workshop and prototype release
4. Newsletters #1 (M09) about the project objectives and first technical achievements and #2 (M13) about technical development and first FAS meeting
5. Participation to key events such as the first FAS meeting or the symposium to be held in the frame of Task 7.2 to report the findings and support dissemination/sharing with other stakeholders; this event may be organised jointly with the FAS meeting

3.4.4. Third phase: M13 to M24 (year 2) – Engaging

This third phase will keep raising awareness on the project objectives and activities but additionally will aim to engaging further relevant stakeholders in the project activities and build relevant linkages with ongoing projects and initiatives, at European, national and local levels.

The third phase will follow different sub-objectives that we plan to achieve by the implementation of different dissemination activities:

1. Improving the evidence-based information disseminated through the project communication tools and level of details regarding the technical achievements of the project: e.g. updating the website “Technology” section, making scientific contributions in relevant journals, conferences and/or books, issuing newsletters and press releases on the occasion of the delivery of major project milestones or output, etc.;

2. Developing sound connections with similar research and innovation projects through e.g. the identification of and participation to key events – with a focus on scientific conferences, the organisation of webinars focusing on some of the ecosystem components, etc.;
3. Making the visibility of the project grow via media presence and increased number of website visits, registrations to the newsletter and number of followers on social media to a significant level;
4. Popularising the project intermediate results especially since the second period will focus on technical developments that may seem dry from an end user perspective; thus, specific efforts will need to be made by all partners to ensure that updates on the project work progress are also accessible and provide at least partial answers to user concerns and wishes.

Specific dissemination activities will seek to mark milestones in the project over this period:

1. MS04 – 2nd Intermediate Integration Workshop; due date: M18.
2. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 2.1. Article on the project website and/or update of “Technology” section;
 - 2.2. Issue of a project newsletter (incl. other news and events);
 - 2.3. Issue of a press release to specialised press and media;
 - 2.4. Social media posts promoting the article, newsletter and press release.
3. MS05 – End of Year 2 and second Forum of Advisory Stakeholders meeting; due date: M24 and MS06 – End of development phase; due date: M24.
4. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of these two milestones:
 - 4.1. News on the project website and update of the “Technology”;
 - 4.2. Interview(s) of FAS members on the project website;
 - 4.3. Issue of a project newsletter (incl. other news and events);
5. Social media posts promoting the article and newsletter.

Key actions during the first phase:

1. Publication of regular news and events on the project website
2. Publication of regular posts on social media accounts
3. Release of a project video explaining the role and advantages of the NESTORE coach
4. Press release #3 (M18) – Second integration workshop and updated prototype
5. Newsletters #3 (M18) about prototype iterations and #4 (M22) about about technical work progress and co-creation methodologies and pilot preparation
6. Participation to key events, in particular scientific ones

3.4.5. Fourth phase: M25 to M36 (year 3) – Promoting

This fourth and final phase will aim, in addition to raising awareness and engaging with strategic stakeholders, to promote the project results and ensure that key third parties take ownership of the main project outcomes. This phase will focus on sustainability, strong engagement and commitment of relevant organisations and companies to the final project results. It will develop exploitation opportunities to ensure the project legacy once the project funding stops. Workshops, demos and webinars will focus on the concrete use and sustainability of project results. The final conference and policy recommendations will come to support the promotion of the project results.

The fourth and final phase will follow different sub-objectives that we plan to achieve by the implementation of different dissemination activities:

1. Making significant contributions to the state of the art by sharing NESTORE findings in evidence-based publications;
2. Sensitizing the wide public to the role and benefits of the NESTORE solution and ensure the acceptance of the technology (in collaboration with evaluation activities undertaken in WP7 and WP8) for future uptake by end users;
3. Exploring exploitation and marketing opportunities and targeting potential markets defined in the Exploitation Plan (see activities and deliverables of WP8).

Specific dissemination activities will seek to mark milestones in the project over this period:

1. MS07 – End of integration and start of full installation in the pilot sites; due date: M26.
2. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 2.1. News on the project website and update of the “Use cases” section to present the different pilot sites and co-creation methodology of NESTORE;
 - 2.2. Issue of a project newsletter (incl. other news and events);
 - 2.3. Issue of a press release to specialised press and media;
 - 2.4. Social media posts promoting the article, newsletter and press release;
 - 2.5. Organisation of pilot workshops and related local dissemination events.
3. MS08 – Mid-Term pilot evaluation; due date: M30.
4. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 4.1. News on the project website and update of the “Use cases” section;
 - 4.2. Interviews of pilot sites participants to feed the website with “User Stories”;
 - 4.3. Issue of a project newsletter (incl. other news and events);
 - 4.4. Social media posts promoting the article, newsletter and press release;
 - 4.5. Organisation of pilot workshops and related local dissemination events.
5. MS09 – End of pilot phase and end of project; due date: M36.
6. Type of dissemination foreseen to support the dissemination of this milestone:
 - 6.1. News on the project website and update of all relevant sections;
 - 6.2. Interviews of pilot sites participants to feed the website with “User Stories”;
 - 6.3. Interviews or feedback articles from general and local FAS members;
 - 6.4. Issue of a project newsletter releasing the final project results;
 - 6.5. Issue of a press release to all press and media contacts;
 - 6.6. Social media posts promoting the article, newsletter and press release;
 - 6.7. Participation to key events to promote the project results;
7. Organisation of a European final conference.

Key actions during the first phase:

1. Publication of regular news and events on the project website
2. Publication of regular posts on social media accounts
3. Press release #4 (M26) – End of integration and kick-off of the pilot phase
4. Press release #5 (M36) – End of the pilot phase and release of project final results

5. Newsletters #5 (M25) about the final technical developments and second FAS meeting; #6 (M28) about the final integration and kick-off of pilots; #7 (M31) about the mid-term pilot phase and final event; and #8 (M36) about final project results
6. Participation to key events
7. Organisation of pilot workshops and related local dissemination events
8. Organisation of final conference

3.5. Dissemination channels

In order to effectively and efficiently reach the scientific dissemination objectives, a broad spectrum of dissemination channels will be engaged. These include:

1. publications in journals, conference proceedings and books,
2. popularised articles and posts in mainstream media, blogs, social media,
3. participation in related academic events, policy workshops, fairs and exhibitions,
4. organisation of physical and virtual events, special sessions and colloquiums,
5. liaison, clustering and networking activities, and
6. press and media relations.

It will be supported by different communication channels and assets both traditional and corporate channels of consortium members and specific ones developed for the sake of the project visibility only and in alignment with the project visual identity defined by NEOS. Dissemination channels and activities that are project specific are described in details in the following sections.

The table below presents the partners dissemination channels while the project specific ones are described in details in the next section of this deliverable. Each partner will appoint a contact person for dissemination. The consortium members, industrial, academic and research partners, through their yearly experience, know-how and expertise will ensure that project results will have the necessary exposure to ensure their successful exploitation and utilization after the project ends.

AGE – AGE PLATFORM EUROPE

WEBSITE

<http://age-platform.eu/>

NEWSLETTER

<http://age-platform.eu/newsletter-coverage>

FACEBOOK

<https://www.facebook.com/ageplatformeurope/>

TWITTER

https://twitter.com/AGE_PlatformEU

LINKEDIN

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/age-platform-europe/>

CONTACT POINT #1 Estelle Huchet
estelle.huchet@age-platform.eu
<https://twitter.com/EsHuchet>

CONTACT POINT #2 Ilenia Gheno
ilenia.gheno@age-platform.eu
https://twitter.com/Ilenia_AGE

CNR – CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE

WEBSITE <http://www.cnr.it/>

NEWSLETTER <http://www.almanacco.cnr.it/reader/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/UfficioStampaCnr/>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/StampaCnr>

CONTACT POINT #1 Rita Bugliosi
rita.bugliosi@cnr.it
+39 0649932021

CONTACT POINT #2 Giovanna Rizzo
giovanna.rizzo@ibfm.cnr.it
+390221717210

EURECAT – FUNDACIÓ EURECAT

WEBSITE <https://eurecat.org/en/>

NEWSLETTER None

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/>

TWITTER https://twitter.com/Eurecat_news?lang=it

FLEX – FLEXTRONICS DESIGN S.R.L.

WEBSITE <https://flex.com/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/flextronicsintl>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/flexintl>

LINKEDIN <https://www.linkedin.com/company/flexintl/>

FSIE – FUNDACIÓ SALUT I ENVELLIMENT UAB

WEBSITE <http://salut-envelliment.uab.cat/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/fundacio.salut.envelliment/>

TWITTER https://twitter.com/fsie_uab

LINKEDIN <https://www.linkedin.com/company/5390324/>

**CONTACT
POINT #1** Enric Pineda
IT developer
+34 4335087
Enric.pineda@uab.cat

HES-SO – HAUTE ECOLE SPECIALISEE DE SUISSE OCCIDENTALE

WEBSITE <https://www.hes-so.ch/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/hesso>

TWITTER https://twitter.com/hes_so

LINKEDIN <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2739184/profile>

LU-CIM – LOUGHBOROUGH UNIVERSITY

WEBSITE <http://www.lboro.ac.uk/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/lborouniversity>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/lborouniversity>

MERID – LA MERIDIANA DUE – SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA SOCIALE

WEBSITE <http://www.coplameridiana.it/>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/www.lameridiana.it/?fref=ts>

NEOS – NEOSPERIENCE

WEBSITE <http://www.neosperience.com/>

NEWSLETTER <https://blog.neosperience.com>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/Neosperience/>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/Neosperience>

LINKEDIN <https://www.linkedin.com/company/165143/>

CONTACT POINT #1 Mario Bello
Marketing and Communication Manager
info@neosperience.com

POLIMI – POLITECNICO DI MILANO

WEBSITE <https://www.polimi.it/>
<http://www.design.polimi.it/>
<http://www.dig.polimi.it/>
<http://www.fondazionepolitecnico.it/>

NEWSLETTER <https://www.polimi.it/in-evidenza/le-newsletter-del-poli/>
<http://www.fondazionepolitecnico.it/stampa/newsletter>

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/polimi>
<https://www.facebook.com/Fondazione.Politecnico.di.Milano>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/polimi>
<https://twitter.com/FondaPoliMi>

LINKEDIN <https://it.linkedin.com/edu/politecnico-di-milano-13843>

CONTACT POINT #1 Mascia Sgarlata
Communication Staff
Politecnico di Milano
(+39) 022399 2511
mascia.sgarlata@polimi.it

CONTACT POINT #2 Elisabetta Caregnato
Communication Manager
Fondazione Politecnico di Milano
(+39) 02 2399 9149
elisabetta.caregnato@fondazione.polimi.it

PREVC – PREVENTIE COLLECTIEF

WEBSITE	http://www.preventie-collectief.nl/
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ROPARDO – ROPARDO S.R.L

WEBSITE	https://ropardo.ro/
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FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/Ropardo.SRL/
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LINKEDIN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ropardo-software-engineering/
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SHU – SHEFFIELD HALLAM UNIVERSITY

WEBSITE	https://www.shu.ac.uk/
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FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/sheffieldhallamuniversity
-----------------	---

TWITTER	https://twitter.com/sheffhallamuni
----------------	---

TUD – TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT

WEBSITE	https://www.tudelft.nl/
----------------	---

FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/TUDelft/
-----------------	---

TWITTER	https://twitter.com/tudelft
----------------	---

LINKEDIN	https://www.linkedin.com/school/tu-delft/
-----------------	---

UB – UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

WEBSITE	http://www.ub.edu/web/ub/ca/
FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/UniversitatdeBarcelona
TWITTER	https://twitter.com/UniBarcelona
LINKEDIN	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-barcelona/

UZH – UNIVERSITY OF ZURICH

WEBSITE	http://www.kommunikation.uzh.ch/de.html
NEWSLETTER	http://www.kommunikation.uzh.ch/de/publishing.html (publications)
FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/uzh.ch/
TWITTER	https://twitter.com/uzh_news?lang=de https://twitter.com/uzh_science?lang=de
LINKEDIN	https://www.linkedin.com/school/uzh/
CONTACT POINT #1	Christina Röcke https://www.linkedin.com/in/croecke/

4. Dissemination channels and tools

This section presents the main project channels and tools to support the visibility, attractiveness, and dissemination of the project results. The section starts with a general presentation of the visual identity of the project before covering both digital (website, social media, web banners, etc.) and physical (brochure, posters, etc.) dissemination tools.

4.1. Project identity and logo

The project brand and visual identity will be set up and directly managed by NEOS, whose graphic expertise led to be designated also to set up and manage the project website (see below).

The Nestore logo portrays the essence of the wisdom through a minimalistic sketch of the Greek hero. According to Homer's Iliad, Nestor is the oldest and wisest of the Greek army chiefs against Troy, and is inclined to recall the historic achievements in his life, which lasted for three "human ages". NESTORE is the best companion and - as the mythological Nestor - can give advice to older people so that they can maintain their wellbeing and their independence at home, based on experience and on understanding the current situation.

The principal logo is vertical (smallest format width 0,8 cm); another format was developed for uses in horizontal space (smallest format width 1,8 cm).

Figure 1 - NESTORE Vertical Logo

Figure 2 - NESTORE Horizontal Logo

The project visual identity respects the following color codes:

Yellow

#FFB400

- R 255
- G 180
- B 0

Orange

#F58018

- R 245
- G 128
- B 24

Grey

#333333

- R 51
- G 51
- B 51

4.2. Website and social media

A project website will serve both the scientific and the general audience, with content addressed to both targets and with the provision of multi-lingual content to serve also the pilot sites (cf. WP7) and cover their languages. The website will be fed regularly with news about the project work progress and results. The long-term objective of the website is to create a community of interested parties around the project to accelerate their involvement, to create awareness of the results and to inform them about the latest evolutions in the field. The content of the website will of course become richer as the project moves forward. The website was set-up by ROPARDO and is available at the following link: www.nestore-coach.eu.

Social networks will be used to flank dissemination efforts in order to reach a wider audience and to facilitate the dialogue with relevant stakeholders. In the past few years, social networks (on the global scale particularly Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) have had a major impact on how people interact online and have attracted users in the millions. In all social networks the following activities are planned: the establishment of a NESTORE account and its active operation; search for relevant stakeholders among network users and their invitation to link up with the project; search for existing relevant groups and the active participation in discussions going on there; announcement of project events and major milestones; etc.

4.3. Fliers and posters

Creating fliers and posters about NESTORE approaches and results will offer a concise and visually-appealing way to disseminate information to broad audiences. The flier will be used to give the interested target groups a spirit of the project and its aims; it will also point the reader towards dissemination channels that are subject to regular updating (such as the project website). This approach offers a chance for personal interaction in academic, commercial and socio-economic conferences, EU organised events and conferences and trade fairs and exhibitions.

A preliminary version of the flyer was developed following the project visual identity. Two versions derived from this generic flyer are going to be developed in the first project months to address two categories of audiences: academic stakeholders and end users.

Figure 3 - NESTORE Generic Flyer (front)

Figure 4 - NESTORE Generic Flyer (back)

4.4. Digital imageries

4.4.1. Web banners and infographics

Following the project visual identity, web banners were developed by NEOS for usage on social media and partners website. As the project moves forward, infographics and other digital imageries representing the NESTORE coach more visually will be developed. These illustrations will support the accessibility, visibility and attractiveness of the project.

4.4.2. Video

A video of NESTORE will be designed to present the general ambition of the project. It will be realised in English and subtitled versions will be provided for the three languages of the pilot sites.

4.5. Press releases

A first press release will be issued during the first six months of the project to describe its objectives, expected results and impact. Project consortium members will also be provided with a general presentation of the project that will be understandable for the public and will help them disseminate preliminary information about their involvement in NESTORE. Press releases (PR) will be issued whenever major milestones of the project are reached.

Press releases will be issued to specialised press and media on the occasion of major technical developments, following the project milestones (subject to adaptation depending on the technical developments of NESTORE):

1. January 2018 (M05) – PR #1 – Project website goes live!
2. May 2018 (M09) – PR #2 – First integration workshop and prototype release
3. February 2019 (M18) – PR #3 – Second integration workshop and updated prototype
4. October 2019 (M26) – PR #4 – End of development and integration phase; all components released and integrated into the NESTORE system; formal kick-off of the pilot phase
5. August 2020 (M36) – PR #5 – End of pilot phase and release of full project documentation and assessment; finalisation of exploitation strategy and release of policy guideline

4.6. Newsletters and fact sheets

A newsletter will be created to keep the different stakeholders informed on the status of the project. A synthetic final report will also be made available to inform them about the main project output especially in case some stakeholders would be interested in exploiting part of the project results.

Newsletters will be published regularly all along the project to a database of stakeholders coming from different EU countries and encompassing the different audiences targeted by NESTORE. These newsletters will cover major technical developments, inform about local activities and end user feedback as well as provide readers with insights from the Forum of Advisory Stakeholders (subject to adaptation depending on the technical developments of NESTORE):

1. May 2018 (M09) – Newsletter #1 about the project objectives and first prototype
2. September 2018 (M13) – Newsletter #2 about technical development and first FAS meeting
3. February 2019 (M18) – Newsletter #3 about prototype iterations
4. June 2019 (M22) – Newsletter #4 about technical work progress and co-creation
5. September 2019 (M25) – Newsletter #5 about all components and second FAS meeting
6. December 2019 (M28) – Newsletter #6 about the final integration and kick-off of pilot phase
7. March 2020 (M31) – Newsletter #7 about the mid-term pilot phase
8. August 2020 (M36) – Newsletter #8 about final project results

4.7. Templates

Two kinds of templates are available: (1) for Word external and internal deliverables and reports, as this document; (2) for PowerPoint presentations including a public set of presentation slides; all templates strongly aligned with the overall design of the logo and visual identity of the project described above. NESTORE partners are asked to use these templates whenever they present the project somewhere or write project-related documents.

5. Publications

A major means to reach target audiences of NESTORE and spread the knowledge gained from research efforts is to make publications in highly prestigious media. The majority of them are expected to happen after the first nine months of the project, when we reach the first key milestones and release system prototypes.

5.1. Publication policy

All publications related to this project will be published in open access journals which are free to access. In order to ensure the effectiveness of the dissemination, a Dissemination Board, chaired by the Scientific Coordinator and constituted by representatives from the project academic partners, will be set up to draw the strategic guidelines for dissemination, identifying high impact journals¹¹ and conferences and ensuring that results are published timely. Work package leaders will be responsible for monitoring the progress of the work, so that papers and presentation can be prepared and published according to the guidelines defined by the Dissemination Board.

In order to increase the visibility of publications, as well as complying with the European Commission's dissemination rules, the NESTORE consortium will pay particular attention to publication accessibility issues by following a 'green' model for free online access. To this end, a dedicated page on the project website will be developed, where all the NESTORE-related publications will be listed in chronological order, grouped by publication year. More specifically, the publications list will present the title, the authors, the type of publication and a short abstract explaining in plain language what the publication is about¹². Additionally, each publication record will be accompanied by two hyperlinks, i.e.:

1. "Publisher" that will redirect to the official webpage of the publisher, from where the publication can be freely accessed or purchased, according the policy of the publisher;
2. "Open-access" that will redirect to the final post-refereeing manuscript accepted for publication, stored to an open access repository, such as Zenodo¹³. This link will be available in case the "Publisher" link does not provide open access.

It should be reminded here that the rules regarding the open access to scientific publications are mentioned clearly in the NESTORE Grand Agreement under article 29.2.

For the sake of consistency, all references and citations in deliverables must be in APA style, except for hyperlinks (online resources) that based on the author's judgment can be inserted as footnotes or as is inside the text. For in-text citations, the APA citation system should only make reference to the author and date in the text thanks to parentheses separated by a comma while the full reference is listed in more details into an accompanying reference list at the end of the document (narrative citation; see example below). If the author's name is in the narrative of the sentence, only the year should be in parentheses (parenthetical citation).

¹¹ Ideally, these journals will be indexed in databases such as PubMed Medline or technology databases.

¹² Given the academic audience these publications are usually targeting, the abstract to be published on the NESTORE website may be different from the abstract usually required in the publication itself for the sake of accessibility.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/>

1. Example narrative citation: In our societies faced by the challenges of ageing demographics, Virtual Coaches offer opportunities to support older adults willing to maintain their quality of life and good health (Guarneri, 2017).
2. Example parenthetical citation: Guarneri (2017) describes the NESTORE Virtual Coach as a very innovative project helping older adults to stay healthy as they age.

The reference list needed at the end of the document should provide the author, date, title, and source of the cited work in an alphabetical list of references. The reference list should only compile sources cited in the text.

5.2. Expected scientific publications

The table below presents a list of some major publications that are expected to be accomplished during the course of the project. It should be highlighted that the above tentative list contains only indicative publications and may be amended according to the course of the project.

Table 2 - Tentative list of major publications by NESTORE partners

TOPIC	TYPE	SUBMISSION
Guarneri R, Rizzo G, Mastropietro A. NESTORE: a Multidomain Virtual Coach for Active and Healthy Ageing, MobiHealth 2017 - 7th EAI International Conference on Wireless Mobile Communication and Healthcare, November 14-15, 2017, Vienna, Austria, in press.	Abstract	14-15/11/2017

5.2.1. Journals, books and chapters

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals, books and chapters constitute a priority for the NESTORE consortium. The following table presents a tentative (non-exclusive) list of relevant journals where the project work could be presented.

Table 3 - Indicative target journals, books and chapters list

TITLE	AIMS AND SCOPE
AGE	It is an international, peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles related to research in the biology of aging and research on biomedical applications that impact aging.
BEHAVIOR RESEARCH METHODS	The journal Behaviour Research Methods publishes articles concerned with the methods, techniques, and instrumentation of research in experimental psychology. The journal focuses particularly on the use of computer technology in

psychological research.

**CAMBRIDGE JOURNAL
ON AGEING AND SOCIETY**

Is an interdisciplinary and international journal devoted to the understanding of human ageing and the circumstances of older people in their social and cultural contexts. In addition to original articles, Ageing & Society publishes book reviews, occasional review articles and special issues.

ELIFE

eLife publishes outstanding research in the life sciences and biomedicine, from the most fundamental and theoretical work, through to translational, applied, and clinical research.

**IEEE JOURNAL OF
BIOMEDICAL AND
HEALTH INFORMATICS**

It publishes original papers describing recent advances in the field of biomedical and health informatics where information and communication technologies intersect with health, healthcare, life sciences and biomedicine.

**IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON
AFFECTIVE COMPUTING**

It is a cross-disciplinary and international archive journal aimed at disseminating results of research on the design of systems that can recognize, interpret, and simulate human emotions and related affective phenomena.

**IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON
BIOMEDICAL
ENGINEERING**

Basic and applied papers dealing with biomedical engineering. Papers range from engineering development in methods and techniques with biomedical applications to experimental and clinical investigations with engineering contributions

**IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON
COMPUTATIONAL
INTELLIGENCE AND AI IN
GAMES**

Papers in computational intelligence and related areas in artificial intelligence applied to games, including but not limited to videogames, mathematical games, human-computer interactions in games, and games involving physical objects. Emphasis is placed on the use of these methods to improve performance in and understanding of the dynamics of games.

**IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON
SIGNAL PROCESSING**

The IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing covers novel theory, algorithms, performance analyses and applications of techniques for the processing, understanding, learning, retrieval, mining, and extraction of information from signals.

INFORMATION FUSION

Papers dealing with fundamental theoretical analyses as well as those demonstrating their application to real-world problems, including: multi-sensor and distributed sensor system design, multi-sensor management and real time applications, biomedical information systems, fusion learning in imperfect, imprecise and incomplete environments

JOURNAL OF AGEING

Explores the complex and dynamic relationship between gerontology and health. A wide variety of disciplines is presented, including Allied Health, Psychology,

AND HEALTH	Public Health, Social Policy and Work, Epidemiology, Health Services Research, Sociology and Nursing.
JOURNAL OF AGING AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	JAPA is the official journal of the International Coalition for Aging and Physical Activity. It is a multidisciplinary peer-reviewed journal examining the dynamic relationship between physical activity and the aging process.
NATURE HUMAN BEHAVIOUR	Nature Human Behaviour features topics that span the behavioural sciences, including perception, memory and learning, reward and decision-making, emotion, language and communication, social cognition and behaviour, and belief systems and culture.
OXFORD JOURNAL ON AGE AND AGEING	Age and Ageing is an international journal publishing refereed original articles and commissioned reviews on geriatric medicine and gerontology. Its range includes research on human ageing and clinical, epidemiological, and psychological aspects of later life.
PHYSIOLOGY AND BEHAVIOR	Physiology & Behaviour is aimed at the causal physio-logical mechanisms of behaviour and its modulation by environmental factors.
SPRINGER MULTIMEDIA TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS	Original research articles on multimedia development and system support tools as well as case studies of multimedia applications. It also features experimental and practical articles in areas related with physiological data sensing and datasets.
THE JOURNAL OF NUTRITION, HEALTH & AGING	A major aim of "The Journal of Nutrition, Health & Aging" is to contribute to the improvement of knowledge regarding the relationships between nutrition and the aging process from birth to old age.

5.2.2. Conferences

Apart from publications in journals, the work of NESTORE will be presented in conferences. A tentative list of such conferences and congresses is presented in the table below.

Table 4 - Indicative target conferences list

TITLE	AIMS AND SCOPE
AI*IA 2018 - 17TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF THE ITALIAN ASSOCIATION FOR ARTIFICIAL	The conference will be open to citizenship, with a theme to be defined but still linked to the artificial intelligence related to the everyday life and the implications and controversies it generates.

INTELLIGENCE**IEEE INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON COMPUTER-BASED MEDICAL SYSTEMS**

Data Analysis and Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Representation, Decision Support and Recommendation Systems, Big Data and Everywhere Data Management, Systems Integration and Security, Biomedical Signal and Image Processing and Machine Vision, Clinical and Healthcare Services Research, Computer-supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) in Healthcare, Medical Education, Robotics, Intelligent Medical Devices and Smart Technologies, Bioinformatics

ELEVIT 2017

Biomedical Engineering

IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ACOUSTICS, SPEECH AND SIGNAL PROCESSING

Audio and acoustic signal processing, Sensor array & multichannel signal processing, Bio-imaging and biomedical signal processing, Signal processing theory & methods, Industry technology tracks, Signal processing for Big Data, Information forensics and security, Internet of Things, Machine learning for signal processing, Speech processing, Multimedia signal processing, Spoken language processing, Remote Sensing and signal processing, Signal Processing for Brain Machine Interface, Signal Processing for Smart Systems

IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON IMAGING SYSTEMS AND TECHNIQUES

Medical diagnostics, translational imaging and theranostics, bioinformatics, biomarkers, metabolites, pharmaco-imaging in drugs and medicine, active-passive sensors and illumination technologies, pharmaceutical and food processing vision inspection systems, image processing and pattern recognition, emerging imaging trends, imaging devices, modalities and techniques, cameras, displays and device miniaturization.

IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PERVASIVE COMPUTING TECHNOLOGIES FOR HEALTHCARE

Pervasive Health Conference is a premier international forum with specific focus on technologies and human factors related to the use of ubiquitous computing in health care and for wellbeing. The overall goal of the Pervasive Health Conference is to take a multidisciplinary approach to Pervasive Healthcare Technology research and development.

IEEE INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON MEDICAL MEASUREMENTS AND APPLICATIONS

Sensors for medical systems / Sensor fusion and calibration; Biosignal processing; Embedded systems; Monitoring of rehabilitation and accelerometry; Medical applications and instrumentation

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF THE IEEE ENGINEERING IN MEDICINE AND BIOLOGY SOCIETY

Biosignal processing, Biomedical imaging, Medical instrumentation and sensors, MEMS and nanotechnology, Neural engineering, Rehabilitation engineering, Biorobotics, Biosystems modelling, Computational bioengineering and bioinformatics

**INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
TECHNOLOGY AND
INNOVATION IS SPORTS,
HEALTH AND WELLBEING**

Sport, Health and wellbeing; Physical activity and healthy lifestyles; Making health and sport facilities more attractive for people.

**INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY
OF BEHAVIORAL
NUTRITION AND
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY**

The ISBNA society stimulates, promotes and advocates innovative research and policy in the area of behavioural nutrition and physical activity toward the betterment of human health worldwide.

**MEASURING BEHAVIOR
2016**

Measuring Behaviour is the premier interdisciplinary event for scientists and practitioners concerned with the study of human or animal behaviour. This unique community and its biannual conference focus on methods, techniques and tools in behavioural re-search in the widest sense. The purpose of this community is to foster scientific discussions regarding methods and techniques in behavioural research.

**THE 2016 MEETING OF
THE BRITISH FEEDING
AND DRINKING GROUP**

The British Feeding and Drinking Group (BFDG) is an interdisciplinary grouping of scientists dedicated to studying human ingestive behaviour and associated conditions, such as eating disorders and obesity. The group draws its membership from academia and industry, and encompasses psychology, physiology, pharmacology, medicine, and nutrition.

5.3. Expected popularised publications

In addition to the communication channels dedicated to the project (website, newsletter, etc.) and the project partners' traditional dissemination tools, NESTORE will be disseminated through mainstream media, specialised press and institutional channels. For instance, the project newsletter and relevant news will be sent to other newsletters and EU news channels, including:

1. The European Commission "eHealth, Wellbeing & Ageing" Newsletter
2. The European Commission "Digital Single Market" Newsletter
3. The European Commission EU Health Policy Platform and the Agora Network
4. The Marketplace of the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing
5. The Covenant on Demographic Change website and newsletter
6. Other European media and blogs, such as Euronews

Any partner contributing to the dissemination of the project through the project channels (e.g. website articles, social media posts, etc.) should provide input consistent with the rest of the content disseminated on that channel. Thus, partners are kindly asked to use UK English and follow the project writing style that is derived from the Guardian guidelines. More information about the NESTORE writing style is available in Annex I.

6. Events

The organisations and the participation to events is a traditional means of dissemination for research and innovation project in order to exchange with stakeholders and interested third parties over the work progress and directions the project is taking. Similarly to publications, most events are expected to be organised or attended after the first nine months of the project, when we reach the first key milestones and release system prototypes.

6.1. Participation in events

6.1.1. Academic events

Academic partners and research institutions will participate in several international academic conferences in order to disseminate the work performed in NESTORE and the project findings. Depending on the topics of the articles, these conferences may include forums related to e.g. mobile health, persuasive technology, social media and social networks, user research methods, usability, information modelling, gaming, digital ecosystems, etc. In addition, publishing articles on the performed research in industry relevant or academic journals is expected.

6.1.2. Commercial events

Industry partners will present NESTORE concepts and prototypes technology in a number of trade shows. Participation to these events will support the development of a network of stakeholders that will aim to foster penetration in specific sectors, get support and advice and use the stakeholders for disseminating the project and exploiting its results. Regarding industrial exhibitions, the following major domains will be considered:

1. Health, fitness and wellness related exhibitions;
2. IT and sensor related exhibitions;
3. Some of the above combined (Health-IT exhibitions).

Most of these events are annual or biannual, and a more detailed planning will be done, based on the locations and the availabilities of partners.

6.1.3. Policy events

Alongside clustering and networking activities and in order to support the dissemination of NESTORE policy recommendations, a participation of NESTORE partners to various networking events will be considered; an indicative list is presented in the table below.

Table 5 - Indicative list of networking events

TITLE	AIMS AND SCOPE
AAL FORUM	The AAL Programme promotes innovative technological product ideas and supports them until they launch on the market. These innovations are presented at the annual AAL Forum, among the largest European events of its kind. The forum provides an excellent opportunity to network within the AAL community

and to discuss issues around AAL within workshops, keynote presentations and a large exhibition area.

EUROPEAN SUMMIT ON INNOVATION FOR HEALTH AND ACTIVE AGEING

Presentation of top-tier solutions for active and healthy ageing and solutions that help prevent falls, counter frailty and cognitive decline, improve care, enable independent living, or enhance social inclusion

EIP ON AHA A3 ACTION GROUP MEETINGS

Discussion based on the development, testing and implementation of new models, strategies and tools for health promotion, disease prevention, empowerment, self-care, community-based interventions and integrated care

EHEALTH STAKEHOLDER GROUP

In 2012, following a call for expression of interest, the European Commission selected 29 members to participate in its eHealth Stakeholder Group. Members of the group, appointed for a period of three years, are expert representatives of European umbrella organisations active in the eHealth sector

EUROPEAN HEALTH FORUM GASTEIN

The EHFG is the leading annual health policy event in the EU. With its wide-ranging three-day programme, the Forum offers an unparalleled platform for decision-makers in various fields of public health & healthcare

6.2. Organisation of events

6.2.1. Local events

Local events involving pilot users will be organised in each country. These local events will be organised jointly and in collaboration with local partners involved in pilot activities in WP7. The organisation of a public event with both the general and local Forum of Advisory Stakeholders as well as interested third parties could be considered during the third dissemination phase depending on the work progress of the research and development activities and the budget available.

6.2.2. Final project event

A final conference will be organised to display the effective results and impact of NESTORE, including new and promising scientific and policy connection, and possible final policy recommendations. This final event will gather both users and stakeholders. The event will include a discussion on the medical validation of NESTORE, its exploitation strategy and exploration of possible synergies with additional stakeholders or related projects that may maximize the impact of the project.

6.2.3. Virtual events including webinars

The organisation of webinars may be considered with scientific partners to disseminate the research results to specific academic audiences.

7. Clustering activities

Communication and dissemination are addressed to set up synergies with other EU and non-EU initiatives with similar or complementary objectives. The project will liaise with relevant platforms, networks and activities for bridging with other research stakeholders at European, national and local level (this will be especially coordinated by AGE which is also in charge of the Fora of Advisory Stakeholders under WP8). Workshops and meetings will be attended or organised for these purposes.

NESTORE will also carefully follow the developments of the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP on AHA), in particular the Action Group A3 dedicated to frailty prevention. NESTORE's participation to the EIP on AHA could be a major dissemination boost, as it would enable the project to collaborate with other organisations that share complementary expertise or that have gone through similar projects. The active participation in the work of the action groups of the EIP on AHA is a way of interacting and having access to organisations that share similar goals and access some of the leading international experts in the field.

Moreover, clustering with other related EU funded projects, especially those performing research on the active and healthy ageing with ICT area and those funded under the same topic as NESTORE (i.e. H2020-EU.3.1.4. - Active ageing and self-management of health), will be actively pursued throughout the project duration. In this context, common areas of interest will be identified and potential fields of co-operation and synergies with respect to these areas will be elaborated. Participation in other projects workshops and meetings can help the exchange of information and good practices. The table below presents an indicative list of projects that NESTORE could liaise with.

Table 6 - Indicative lists of (EU funded) related projects

TITLE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	FINISH DATE
ACTIVAGE	ACTIVAGE is a European Multi Centric Large Scale Pilot on Smart Living Environments. The main objective is to build the first European IoT ecosystem across 9 Deployment Sites (DS) in seven European countries, reusing and scaling up underlying open and proprietary IoT platforms, technologies and standards, and integrating new interfaces needed to provide interoperability across these heterogeneous platforms, that will enable the deployment and operation at large scale of Active & Healthy Ageing IoT based solutions and services, supporting and extending the independent living of older adults in their living environments, and responding to real needs of caregivers, service providers and public authorities. http://www.activageproject.eu/	30/06/2020
AEQUALIS	With the aim to reduce health inequality, an intervention has been designed to promote self-management, health literacy and social capital among older people who perceived their health as fair or poor and are living in urban socioeconomically disadvantaged areas with the aim of improving their self-	31/12/2017

perceived health. Secondly, the efficacy of the intervention will be analysed in terms of increasing self-management, health literacy and social capital (social support and social participation), quality of life, mental health and healthy lifestyles. In third place, behavioural health patterns will be identified in relation to health literacy, social capital, gender, socioeconomic and educational level, and they will be linked to the intervention efficacy levels.

<http://salut-envelliment.uab.cat/aequalis/ca/>

APTITUDE

The general objective of APTITUDE (Agir pour la Prévention Transpyrénéenne de la Dépendance chez les seniors) is to deploy in the cross-border area of the Pyrenees a project to prevent dependence among seniors by creating a network to promote care, training, research and innovation in gerontology. It is divided into 3 axes: (1) Creation of the Trans-Pyrenees Network of Aging and Prevention of Dependency Prevention (RTVPD), based in France on an operational network (ERVPD Occitanie); (2) Training / information for health professionals, the general public, associations, biomedical and pharmaceutical companies; (3) Identification of SMEs and start-ups working in the field of ageing to develop innovative actions and the Silver Economy with the research teams and thus create an ecosystem of scientists, industrial players and patient associations.

31/12/2020

CAPTAIN

CAPTAIN proposes a “transparent” technology designed to turn the home of the older adult into a ubiquitous assistant specifically designed to compensate for their physical and memory impairments during their daily living. The coach will leverage on a motivational engine to promote correct nutrition, physical activity, cognitive and physical training, risk avoidance, and social participation. To achieve this CAPTAIN will foster a truly user-centred co-design philosophy -based on constant involvement of older adult in the design, development, and testing stages.

30/11/2020

COUCH

Despite the proliferation of ICT solutions for personalized healthcare, there is still no easy way to provide older adults with integrated coaching services. Council of Coaches (COUCH) introduces a radically new virtual coaching concept based on multiple autonomous, embodied virtual coaches, which form together a personal council that fulfils the needs of older adults in an integrated way.

31/08/2020

DOREMI

This project studies early signs of unhealthy dietary habits, sedentariness and cognitive decline. By recording and monitoring information about the use of the lifestyle-changing tools and programmes, it will be possible to track user’s performance over

31/10/2016

long periods, providing early warning of signs of malnutrition, physical and cognitive deterioration.

<http://www.doremi-fp7.eu/>

EMPATHIC

The EMPATHIC Research & Innovation project will research, innovate, explore and validate new paradigms and platforms, laying the foundation for future generations of Personalised Virtual Coaches to assist elderly people living independently at and around their home.

31/10/2020

FRAILSAFE

FrailSafe aims to better understand frailty and its relation to co-morbidities; to identify quantitative and qualitative measures of frailty and use them to predict short and long-term outcome and risk of frailty; to develop real life sensing and intervention (guidelines, real-time feedback, Augmented Reality serious games) platform offering physiological reserve and external challenges; to create “prevent-frailty” evidence-based recommendations for the elderly; to strengthen the motor, cognitive, and other “anti-frailty” activities through the delivery of personalised treatment programmes, monitoring alerts, guidance and education; and to achieve all with a safe, unobtrusive and acceptable system for the ageing population while reducing the cost of health care systems.

31/12/2018

<http://frailsafe-project.eu/>

ICT4LIFE

ICT4Life aims to provide new services for integrated care employing user-friendly ICT tools, ultimately increasing patients with Parkinson’s, Alzheimer’s and other dementias and their caregivers’ quality of life and autonomy at home. The ICT4Life Platform is being developed to deliver a series of innovative services which will connect patients, caregivers and health professionals supporting them.

<http://www.ict4life.eu/>

JAM TODAY

Jam Today supports the creation, implementation and deployment of educational games. Game jams are events typically organised for 48 hours and simultaneously conducted in different locations. They gather game developers, programmers, designers who develop an idea into an innovative solution, i.e. a game, around a specific theme. Jam Today brings together different people who are involved in the process of designing and deploying game-based approaches to learning. Particular attention will be paid to the inclusion of vulnerable groups such as children at risk and the elderly.

31/12/2016

<http://www.jamtoday.eu/>

LO MAPT	The objective of LoMapt (Low Omega 3 Alzheimer Preventive Trial) is to assess the effects of omega-3 on the cognitive deterioration of people aged 70 and over with low levels of omega-3 and subjective complaints of memory or family history of Alzheimer's disease.	31/12/2022
PROMISS	In Europe, between 13.5 and 29.7% of older adults living at home are malnourished or at risk for malnutrition. PROMISS aims at better understanding and preventing malnutrition among them, contributing to improve active and healthy ageing. Using large scale databases, PROMISS will identify the relationships between food intake, food characteristics, physical activity, the oral and gut microbiota, poor appetite, malnutrition and poor health among older adults. Based on the outcomes it develops strategies and new food concepts to address malnutrition. http://www.promiss-vu.eu/	31/03/2021
REMI	The REMI program aims to contribute to the prevention of cognitive impairment in dependent elderly people, as well as the reduction of symptoms in those who already have it. Its design, based on Reminiscence Therapy, has been an initiative of the Foundation for Health and Aging (FSiE) of the Autonomous University of Barcelona. The Catalan Association of Assistive Resources (ACRA) participates as a partner in its development and dissemination plan in Catalonia.	N/A
SAAM	Within the SAAM project (Supporting Active Aging through Multimodal coaching) we focus upon innovative, technology-enabled approaches to support the aging population living at home, with a novel and practical emphasis on ambient sensing and learning of user needs and preferences, and effective coaching by leveraging the user's social support networks.	30/09/2020
SITLESS	To assess the long-term effectiveness (18 month follow-up) of a complex intervention on sedentary behaviour (SB) and physical activity (PA) in a community dwelling older population based on existing exercise referral schemes (ERS) enhanced by self-management-strategies (SMS). http://sitless.eu/	31/05/2019
SPLENDID	SPLENDID focuses on behavioural aspects and modelling behaviour, sensors and information processing, assessment of risk, goal description, setting and monitoring, personalised health systems that are relevant to NESTORE, and also proposes daily life usage like SPLENDID@School, which are worth considering as	31/09/2016

examples.

<http://splendid-program.eu/>

SUNFRAIL

SUNFRAIL “Reference Sites Network for Prevention and Care of Frailty and Chronic Conditions in community dwelling persons of EU Countries” aims at improving the identification, prevention and management of frailty and care of multimorbidity in community dwelling persons (over 65) of loco-regional settings of EU countries.

31/10/2017

<http://www.sunfrail.eu/>

UNCAP

UNCAP develops a system for remote health status monitoring, qualitative and quantitative assessment and treatment personalisation for people suffering from neurodegenerative diseases and movement disorders through the employment of a wide range of wearable micro-sensors, knowledge processing and algorithms.

31/12/2017

<http://www.uncap.eu/>

XARES

XARES’ objective is to establish a network collaboration structure between centres belonging to the Vallparadís Foundation of the Mútua de Terrassa group, MUTUAM and FSiE for the creation of a repository of data from a set Consensual of variables that serves to generate knowledge about the population given that it allows: (1) Improve the quality of care of the centres and provide better attention to their users; (2) Improve or extend as long as possible the quality of life, welfare, satisfaction, autonomy and health status of people living in residence.

N/A

8. Dissemination evaluation

Dissemination metrics and impact indicators should be defined in order to evaluate the efficiency of the overall dissemination activities, targeting either the scientific community or the end-users and stakeholders. The analysis of these metrics will unveil possible weaknesses in the dissemination process and will help the consortium understand how to improve the overall effort. These metrics are described in the sections below.

8.1. Monitoring of work progress

AGE as Task leader will regularly remind partners about the dissemination activities they delivered and will deliver, as foreseen in the dissemination plan. There will be also specific dissemination campaigns around key milestones, events or activities, as the project moves forward. As Dissemination Manager, AGE is part of the project Steering Board and will take the opportunity of regular teleconferences to remind partners of their communication and dissemination obligations.

Each year, together with the project coordinator POLIMI, AGE will use the Communication and Dissemination Reports to report on the activities carried out and adapt the dissemination activities to be implemented over the next period. Key information will be required on quantitative data (numbers) and qualitative data (communication impact/results). Templates to record dissemination activities and gather information on each of the communication tools will be available to partners (see next paragraph), so they are informed on the exact type of information required when planning their communication activities.

8.2. Recording of activities

In order to keep track of the publications, a dedicated “NESTORE Publications Record” online document will be created and made available to all partners. When a publication is achieved, the responsible partner should add a record with all the required corresponding details, i.e., type of publication, reference, official link, repository, link to repository and partner responsible. The filled-in document will act as a guide and will allow the leader of the dissemination task (Task 1.4) to evaluate and correct the planned actions.

In order to document important characteristics (type of event, location, date, who attended, activities and number of attendees) of such dissemination activities, a dedicated “NESTORE Event Record” Google Sheets document will be created and will be available online to all partners. The filled-in document will be subsequently summarized into tables, composing a list of concrete actions that will allow the leader of the dissemination task (Task 1.4) to evaluate, follow up and correct the planned actions.

8.3. Evaluation of impact

Depending on the nature of an action, there are certain indicators that can actually imply the achieved impact:

1. the number of unique visits/views of the project website that are intended to provide the viewer with information around a certain topic (tools like “Google Analytics” or similar are usually employed to capture this indicator);

2. the number of followers/friends/connections, which is an indicator that has become popular due to the widespread adoption of social networks. Accounts with high popularity are typically considered more influential than others;
3. the number of publications (journals, conferences, book chapters and books) along with the impact factor/acceptance rate; this is a typical indicator that shows the impact of project activities/results to the related scientific community;
4. the number of events organised/attended along with the number of participants; this is a rather generic indicator that can be valid for all different types of events (from workshops to fairs and roadshows) and is used to provide a rough estimate about the number of people that actually received the dissemination message.

The table below presents a list of all activities along with the impact indicators and the way to be measured.

Table 7 - Dissemination impact indicators

ACTIVITIES OR CHANNELS	IMPACT INDICATORS	SOURCES
WEBSITE	Number of visits	Google Analytics
	Time spent per visit	Google Analytics
	Number of new compared to number of returning visitors	Google Analytics
FLYER	Number of leaflet disseminated	Project reporting
PRESS RELEASES	Number of press releases issued	Project reporting
	Number of recipients of press releases	MailChimp
SOCIAL MEDIA	Number of followers on Twitter account	Twitter
	Number of likes on Facebook page	Facebook
	Number of followers on LinkedIn group	LinkedIn
VIDEO	Number of views	YouTube
CONFERENCES, FAIRS AND EVENTS	Number of events with a NESTORE presence	Project reporting

	Number of workshops organised by NESTORE	Project reporting
	Attendance to events organised by NESTORE	Participants' lists
	Gender balance in events organised by NESTORE	Participants' lists
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS	Number of scientific publications	Project reporting
POPULARISED PUBLICATIONS	Number of popularised publications	Project reporting
EXPLOITATION	Possible collaborations with industry	Project reporting

9. Conclusion

The dissemination plan outlined in this document shows how “Task 1.4” will organise its activities towards the scientific dissemination of the NESTORE results in the relevant communities. To this end, a dissemination strategy has been defined, incorporating the dissemination objectives, target audiences and a detailed description of dissemination tools (publications, events, academic actions and clustering activities). Updates of this plan, as well as reporting of future activities, will be included in the periodic reports.

Indice

AAL – Active and Assisted Living

AGE – AGE Platform Europe

AHA – Active and Healthy Ageing

CO – Confidential

D – Deliverable

EC – European Commission

EU – European Union

EIP on AHA – European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing

GNAFCC – Global Network of Age-Friendly Cities and Communities

ICT – Information and Communication Technology

IoT – Internet of Things

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

M – Month

MS – Milestone

N/A – Not applicable

R&D – Research and Development

T – Task

WP – Work Package

WHO – World Health Organisation

Annex I – Writing guidelines

The following is a brief guide to the NESTORE writing style in case you are contributing to any dissemination content (the following does not apply to scientific publications). If you have a query about a point of style not covered below, please consult the Guardian style guide: www.guardian.co.uk/styleguide

GENDER SENSITIVE COMMUNICATION RULES

To ensure your communication is gender sensitive, we recommend you to follow the six principles of gender sensitive communications from the UNDP Gender Equality Seal:

<http://www.jm.undp.org/content/dam/jamaica/docs/gender/JM-AUG-29-UNDP%20Gender%20Seal-Principles%20of%20gender-sensitive%20communications.pdf>

1. **Ensure that women and men are represented** – e.g. that quotes from both men and women are included in communications, that female voices or images are presented in traditionally male roles and vice versa, etc.
2. **Challenge gender stereotypes** – avoid representing certain vocations or roles as only appropriate for, or held by, by women and men (e.g. doctors are men, nurses are women), avoid using phrases that stereotype women's or men's behavior (e.g. women and girls are timid in comparison to men and boys, or that females are passive and males are active).
3. **Avoid exclusionary forms** – one can use “he” and “she” to be inclusive, or use the plural ‘they’ to avoid using any gendered pronouns.
4. **Use equal forms of address** – avoid addressing women by their marital status or referred to women as someone's partner instead of an individual in their own right.
5. **Create a gender balance** – avoid generics or gender-specific terms such as ‘fatherland’, ‘mankind’, ‘mother tongue’ and prefer gender-sensitive alternative e.g. ‘Native tongue’.
6. **Promote gender equity through titles, labels, and names** – instead of using actress or stewardess, for women professionals, it is better to use the generic term (actor or flight attendant) to avoid promoting gender inequality.

PUNCTUATION

- Use hyphens when describing ‘hour-to-hour’, ‘minute-to-minute’ etc.
- In terms of full-stops within bullets, if the bullet is a complete sentence then use a full stop (as here).

NUMBERS

- Numbers zero to nine should be written out in full.

- Numbers 10 and above should be written numerically.
- **Except** when using a decimal point (eg 9.3), all numbers are to be numerical.
- Numbers in tables should be written out numerically.

ABBREVIATIONS

- When starting a sentence with “for example” or “for instance”, always write the words out in full. However, when it is appropriate to abbreviate these terms (e.g. in the middle of a sentence, within brackets etc.) always use the full-stops: ‘e.g.’ and ‘i.e.’.
- ‘etc’ doesn’t need a full-stop when it’s within a sentence.

COMMON STYLE ISSUES

- **Monetary amounts:** €10 million and €20 billion – never €10m or €20bn.
- **% vs per cent:** 100% – never 100 per cent or percent.
- **Job titles** are lower-case – ‘managing director’

EXTRA NOTES

- **Always use English spelling.** E.g. colour not color; realise not realize; centre not center.
- **Check for double spacings.** They are ugly and should be deleted immediately.
- Keep sentences and paragraphs short. Break them up where necessary.
- **Avoid splitting/hyphenating words** throughout the text. Drop the word down to a new line instead.
- Never use capitals to emphasise words. Use capitals for acronyms only.
- **Think about paragraph construction.** To avoid a paragraph becoming repetitive, try not to use the same words too often if you can find alternatives. For example, interchange ‘may’ for ‘might’, ‘can’, ‘possibly’, etc.
- **Use double quote marks (“)** for quotes and single quote marks for quotes within quotes.
- **Give a person’s name (and job title if relevant) in full on the first mention.** Then, for most stories/features, use first name. Stick to surnames for politicians, VIPs, celebrities.

Annex II – Word Template use guidelines

INDEX OF CONTENTS

To create an item of the Index of Content: select text of the title of a paragraph and apply style: "Nestore_TITLE" from the "Change Style" list.

To update data in the Index of Content: select the index area ("Table of Content") and apply command "Update field".

FIGURES AND INDEX OF FIGURES

In order to create and manage figures and list of figures:

- go to "Insert"
- select "Image" and insert the image in the document
- select the inserted Image
- apply style: "Image" from the "Change Style" list
- go to "References"
- go to "Insert Caption", select Label: "Figure"

To create the List of Figures:

- go to "Insert Table of Figures"
- select Caption label: "Figure"

To update data: select the index and apply command "Update field"

TABLES AND INDEX OF TABLES

In order to manage tables and list of tables:

- go to "Insert"
- select "Table" and draw a Table
- select the table
- go to "Table Design"

- apply "Nestore_Table" type from the table layouts list
- go to "References"
- select "Insert Caption", select label: "Table"

To create the List of Table:

- go to "Insert Table of Figures"
- select Caption label: "Table"

To update data: select the index and apply command "Update field"

INSERT FOOTNOTE

In order to create a footnote referring to a word or more within the text:

- select the word or text
- go to "Insert Footnote"
- write the note in the form

GENERATE WORDS INDEX

In order to generate new item in the Index:

- select the word
- go to "Mark Entry"
- fill in the form

To update data:

- go to "References"
- apply "Update Index"

